

Mitigating Strategies For Enteric Methane Emissions In Ruminants: An Overview On Sustainable Alternatives

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ABSTRACT

Methane emitted by the ruminants is considered as an important contributor to the global warming. The enteric methane production in ruminants not only increases environmental pollution but also negatively impacts their productivity consequently leading to economic losses for farmers. Many attempts have been tried to manipulate the rumen microbial ecosystem using antibiotics, synthetic chemicals and dietary interventions to reduce the enteric methane emissions in ruminants. Phytogetic feed additives have recently emerged as one of the best alternatives to these antibiotics and synthetic chemicals because of growing public awareness about drug resistance and antibiotic residues. These phytogetic feed additives contain many bioactive compounds, capable of manipulating the rumen microbial ecology by inhibition of the activities of protozoa, methanogenic archaea, and fibrolytic microbes due to its antimicrobial potential and decreasing H₂ availability. In this review, we highlighted the beneficial effects of various phytogetic feed additives on enteric methane emission and other rumen parameters.

Keywords: Global warming, rumen microbial ecosystem, phytogetic feed additives, protozoa and methanogenic archaea.

INTRODUCTION

Global warming is considered as one of the most critical and concerning issue worldwide. The phenomenon of global warming, primarily driven by the human induced accumulation of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, poses a major threat to our planet and its ecosystems (Bajoria *et al.*, 2024). Due to increase in greenhouse gas emissions, the global surface temperature has increased by 1.1 °C between 2011 and 2020 (Bilgili *et al.*, 2024). The dominant green house gases (GHG) produced by anthropogenic activity are Carbon Dioxide (CO₂), Nitrous Oxide (N₂O) and Methane (CH₄) (Yin *et al.*, 2025). Methane (CH₄), produced during enteric fermentation, have higher global warming potential (28–34 times) than that of CO₂ (Huang *et al.*, 2026). The growth in global methane emissions mostly occurred after 1950 and was mainly contributed by livestock sector (Zhang *et al.*, 2022). The livestock production contributes 12% of global methane emissions, as methane is a normal product of ruminant digestion (Symeon *et al.*, 2025).

However, the contribution of enteric methane emissions to global greenhouse gases is relatively low (Güler, 2024). Cattle are the primary contributor of methane emissions compared to other ruminants like sheep and goat because of their size and quantity (Broucek *et al.*, 2014). In ruminant, the enteric methane emissions also reflect a loss of up to 12% of feed's energy that would instead be used for animal productivity (Malyugina *et al.*, 2025). In ruminants, the digestion of feed stuff is accomplished by a complex microbial ecosystem constituting bacteria, archaea, protozoa, and fungi and transforms it into highly valuable products for human consumption (Tardiolo *et al.*, 2025). During ruminal fermentation, various gases are produced, primarily hydrogen and carbon dioxide (Zheng *et al.*, 2026). Inside the rumen, methanogens utilize these two gases for methane production, which eructated out into the atmosphere (Hosen *et al.*, 2025). Feed additives are commonly used in ruminant nutrition for their many beneficial effects like animal growth promoter, toxin binder,

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

breakdown of anti-nutritional factors and reducing methane emission (Dhanasekaran *et al.*, 2020). Plant secondary metabolites are low-molecular-weight organic compounds found in plants; mainly include phenolics, terpenoids, alkaloids and flavonoids (Wu *et al.*, 2025). In recent years, many studies suggested that plant secondary metabolites like saponins, tannins and essential oil, have the ability to manipulate rumen fermentation in a positive way, thus can be used as natural feed additives for improving ruminant production systems and reducing methane emission (Kumar *et al.*, 2025; Holik *et al.*, 2025; Nasir *et al.*, 2025). This review focuses to evaluate the best ways to decrease enteric methane emissions by the use of environment friendly additives of plants origins such as saponins, tannins and essential oils in animal nutrition.

Effect of Feeding Saponins on Enteric Methane Emission

Methanogenesis is the main pathway of hydrogen disposal during the feed fermentation in side rumen. This methane production may be decreased by an inhibition of hydrogen production or by a shift in hydrogen allocation. Both these mechanisms lead to a reduction of H₂ availability for methanogenic archaea (Guyader *et al.*, 2015). Many studies have revealed the positive effects of the plant extracts such as saponins and tannins in mitigating methane emissions (Jayanegara, *et al.*, 2020). Saponins are naturally occurring plants secondary metabolites that are important in human and animal nutrition. The structure of saponins consists of a hydrophilic sugar moiety linked to a lipophilic aglycone, making them amphiphilic in nature. Saponins exhibit surface-active properties, creating stable foams and forming complexes with other molecules (Timilsena *et al.*, 2023). Both *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* studies revealed that saponin from different plant sources have the potential to improve animal production and reduce enteric methane production. However, the beneficial effect of saponins supplementation depends upon the dose and type of substrate used. In an *in-vitro* study, methane production was reduced up to 39, 24 and 25%, when tea saponins were used at level of 0.6% in three substrates having different concentrate to roughage. In the same experiment, the reduction in methane production was observed by 17, 7 and 14% when tea

seeds powder was used as a raw source of saponin in the same level (Kumar *et al.*, 2025). This study also revealed that beneficial results were obtained when crude saponin mixture was used as compare to tea seed powder which was added as a raw source of saponin in all three substrates. In an another *in vitro* study, decrease in methane production was observed when tea seed saponin was added at levels of 0.0%, 0.3%, 0.4%, 0.5%, 0.6%, 0.7%, 0.8%, 0.9% and 1.0% of substrate using low forage diet (forage: concentrate, 30:70), a medium forage diet (forage: concentrate, 50:50) and a high forage diet (forage: concentrate, 70:30) (Jadhav *et al.*, 2018). Tea saponin levels directly reduced enteric methane production by reducing ruminal microbial populations (Yanza *et al.*, 2023). The above studies suggested that tea seed saponins and tea seeds have the potential to modify the rumen fermentation pattern by reducing methane and ammonia release, thus beneficial for improving the animal growth and nutrient utilization. Another *in vitro* study revealed maximum reduction in methane production up to 29% and protozoa concentration up to 51%, when increasing dosage of the tea saponin extracts were added in the substrate using *in vitro* batch culture incubations using bovine rumen contents as inoculum and a cereal mixture as substrate (Guyader *et al.*, 2017). The *Delonix regia* seed meal, which is high in tannins and saponins, was when added at levels of 0, 3.3, 5.0, 6.7, 8.3, 10, 11.7, 13.3, 15.0 and 16.7 mg in a substrate having 70:30 roughage and concentrate ratio (*in-vitro*), methane production was reduced with increasing levels of *Delonix regia* seed meal in the diet ($P < 0.05$) (Supapong *et al.*, 2017). One *in-vitro* study was conducted to assess the effect of a composite plant extract (CPE) rich in polyphenolics and saponins on ruminal fermentation and methanogenesis, using seeds of *Dolichos biflorus* (horse gram), root of *Asparagus racemosus* (shatavari), bark of *Amoora rohituka* (rohitaka), and peel of *Punica granatum* (pomegranate). The results showed decrease in methane and ammonia concentration and increase in dry matter digestibility with increasing doses of composite plant extract (Shilwant *et al.*, 2023). *Aspergillus niger* β -glucosidase-modified alfalfa saponins when were used in an *in-vitro* rumen fermentation study, the Methanogen abundance reduced by 20.10–44.93%, and general anaerobic

fungi reduced by 34.22–44.66%. This *in vitro* findings revealed that enzyme-treated alfalfa saponins modulates rumen fermentation pattern through methane mitigation and increased nutrient utilization, making it a sustainable feed additive strategy for livestock (Zhang *et al.*, 2025). Decrease in Methane yield was observed due to presence of plants secondary metabolites in quinoa plant, when different strains of silage quinoa were used in an *in-vitro* study. These findings suggest that feeding quinoa silage to ruminants has the potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Ge *et al.*, 2025). Soapnut fruits have high saponin content about 10% of fruits. Soapnut powder was when added @ 0, 1, 2, up to 8% on DM basis with substrate in 100ml *in vitro* syringe, the *in-vitro* methane gas production decreased by 22.16 and 15.79% with 1 and 2% of soapnut (Rathod *et al.*, 2024). The *Yucca schidigera* extract (YSE) and *Quillaja saponaria* extract have a suppressing effect on rumen methane production due to antiprotozoal action (Pen *et al.*, 2006). However, one study revealed that the increasing *Yucca schidigera* saponin extract inclusion increased the propionate proportion *in vitro* but there was no reduction observed in methane production (Trotta *et al.*, 2023). Saponins may decrease methane production due to defaunation effect and/or directly by decreasing the activities and numbers of methanogens (Patra and Saxena, 2009). Results of above studied showed that dietary supplementation of saponin decreased enteric methane emission in ruminants for both low and high levels of saponin in the diet. Hence it is recommended that the saponin is effective to reduce enteric methane emission from ruminants provided that its level of use should not exceed 0.5% of DM (Ridla *et al.*, 2021).

Effect of Feeding Tannins on Enteric Methane Emission

Tannins (hydrolysable and condensed tannin) are polyphenolic compounds of relatively high molecular weight with the ability to form complexes with proteins due to the presence of a large number of phenolic hydroxyl groups in their structure (Patra and Saxena, 2011). They are widely distributed in forage trees, shrubs and legumes, cereals and grains. Tannins found in various feed stuffs can affect microbial activity, fermentation processes, protein degradation, and methane production in the rumen (Holik *et al.*,

2025). One study was conducted by feeding tannin-containing hays to heifers and mature beef cows and its effects on enteric methane (CH₄) emissions and nitrogen (N) excretion were evaluated. The results suggest that tannin-containing hays have the potential to reduce urinary urea nitrogen excretion, increase nitrogen retention, and reduce enteric methane emissions from beef cattle (Stewart *et al.*, 2019). In cows, diet supplemented with chestnut, quebracho, and seaweed tannins (@ 200 g/day significantly reduced the total protozoan count, as well as the abundance of main protozoan groups (Holotrichs and Entodiniomorphids) in the rumen (P < 0.05) (Holik *et al.*, 2025). These findings suggested that dietary supplementation of tannins affects ruminal protozoan composition and the rumen microbial community, and have anti-methanogenic potential. The study suggested that dietary tannins suppress rumen methane production by reducing the population of protozoan. When tannic acid supplemented @ 6.5, 13.0 or 26.0 g/kg DM in four adult Simmental male cattle, there was decrease in (p < 0.01) methane production by 11.1%, 14.7% and 33.6%, respectively (Yang *et al.*, 2017). In an another study, four legumes with different concentrations of condensed tannins (CT) were tested: alfalfa (ALF); birdsfoot trefoil (BFT); crown vetch (CV); and sericea lespedeza (SL). The CT concentrations were 3, 21, 38 and 76 g/kg of DM for ALF, BFT, CV, and SL diets, respectively. Total CH₄ production (mg of CH₄/d) was lower (P < 0.001) in the sericea lespedeza supplemented diet in comparison to other 3 diets (Roca-Fernández *et al.*, 2020). Another study was conducted using different legumes rich in condensed tannins (CT) *in vitro* and their effect was observed on methane emissions and rumen microbiota in beef cattle. The results revealed that *Leucaena leucocephala*, *Desmodium paniculatum* and *Lespedeza procumbens* have the potential to suppress rumen methane production (Fagundes *et al.*, 2020). Inclusion of 80% of *Leucaena leucocephala* in the diet of heifers fed low-quality tropical forages has the ability to reduce up to 61.3% enteric methane emission without affecting Dry Matter Intake and protozoa population in rumen liquor (Piñeiro-Vázquez *et al.*, 2017). One study was conducted to evaluate the long-term effects of feeding hydrolyzable tannin (HT) with or without condensed tannin (CT) on animal performance, rumen

fermentation and methane production in beef cattle fed a high-forage diet. This study concluded that a combination of HT and CT at a concentration of 1.5% dietary DM tended to decrease methane emissions without affecting animal performance (Aboagye *et al.*, 2018). In sheep, the inclusion of soybean oil or soybean oil plus tannins reduced methane production and decreased rumen protozoa compared to control treatment ($P < 0.01$) (Lima *et al.*, 2019). The use of low levels of tannin extract from *Acacia mearnsii* have shown to reduce rumen protozoa and methane production and is considered as a potential option to manipulate rumen fermentation in Nellore and Holstein cattle (Perna Junior *et al.*, 2023). One study aimed to compare *in vitro* rumen fermentation characteristics and to evaluate the effects of condensed tannins (CT) on methane production in dairy cattle (*Bos taurus taurus*), zebu beef cattle (*Bos taurus indicus*), water buffaloes (*Bubalus bubalis*), sheep (*Ovis aries*) and goats (*Capra hircus*) using Acacia (*Acacia molissima*) tannin extract and fed similar diets. The results showed that bovines emitted more methane than small ruminants as measured on a degraded organic matter basis. Condensed tannins have greater effects in large ruminants than in small ruminants (Bueno *et al.*, 2015). A study was carried out to investigate how low-dose tannic acid (T), tea polyphenols (TP), and their combination (T+TP; 50:50) affects rumen microbiota and its function in Holstein cows. Compared with the control group, all diets supplemented with additives significantly reduced enteric methane production (13.68% for T, 11.40% for TP, and 10.89% for T+TP) and significantly increased milk protein yield (Zhao *et al.*, 2025). Tannin-containing tropical tree leaves, *Autocarpus integrifolius*, *Azadirachta indica* and *Ficus bengalensis*, when included in optimum doses in the ruminant diets, suppress methanogenesis (Bhatta *et al.*, 2015). The addition of quebracho tannins extract (QTE) at 2 or 3% of dry matter ration can decrease methane production up to 29 and 41%, respectively, without significantly compromising feed intake and nutrients digestibility in cattle fed low-quality *Pennisetum purpureum* grass. (Piñeiro-Vázquez *et al.*, 2018). In an *in vitro* study, tannin extracts were isolated from four different forage species: birdsfoot trefoil (*Lotus corniculatus*), sulla (*Hedysarum coronarium*), big trefoil (*Lotus pedunculatus*), and salad burnet (*Sanguisorba minor*)

decreased the methane (CH₄) production compared to the control group. The highest CH₄ reduction (15%, at 30 g/kg DM) was observed from sulla and big trefoil extracts indicating importance of tannins in animal nutrition (Verma *et al.*, 2024). The cell membrane, cell wall, and glycocalyx of methanogen contain adhesin protein. It is possible that condensed tannins bind to this adhesin or parts of the cell wall, preventing the formation of methanogen-protozoan complexes and reducing interspecies H₂ transfer and thus reducing the methane emission (Ng *et al.*, 2016).

Effect of Feeding Essential Oils on Enteric Methane Emission

Essential oils are blends of secondary metabolites obtained from the plant by a type of distillation, such as hydro distillation, steam distillation, or microwave assisted dry distillation (Sadgrove *et al.*, 2015). Terpenoids (including monoterpenoids and sesquiterpenoids) and phenylpropanoids are the most important bioactive compounds in essential oils (Calsamiglia *et al.*, 2007). The natural feed additives like garlic oil (GO), garlic powder (GP), allicin (ALL), *yucca schidigera* plant extract (Yucca), and an essential oil blend (EO), have shown positive effects as rumen microbiome modifiers (Hodge *et al.*, 2025). Essential oils from Garlic and cinnamon have shown to reduce methane emissions; but they can also reduce *in vitro* dry matter digestibility (Molho-Ortiz *et al.*, 2022). In an *in-vitro* study, two optimal blends of cinnamon and peppermint oils (80:20) and anise and clove oils (80:20) significantly reduced total gas and methane production compared to controls, with the cinnamon-peppermint blend achieving the highest methane reduction. These results suggested the potential use of essential oil blends as effective, sustainable alternatives to conventional feed additives in animal production (Nasir *et al.*, 2025). Four essential oils (EO) isolated from *Achillea santolina*, *Artemisia judaica*, *Schinus terebinthifolius* and *Mentha microphylla*, and supplemented at four levels (0, 25, 50 and 75 µl) to 75 ml of buffered rumen fluid plus 0.5 g of substrate in an *in vitro* study. The main components of the EO were piperitone (49.1%) and camphor (34.5%) in *A. judaica*, 16-dimethyl 15-cyclooctadiene (60.5%) in *A. santolina*, piperitone oxide (46.7%) and *cis*-piperitone oxide (28%) in *M. microphylla*, and γ -muurolene (45.3%) and α -thujene (16.0%) in *S.*

terebinthifolius. The essential oils from *Achillea santolina* and *Artemisia judaica*, and *Mentha microphylla* inhibited the methane production and reduced the protozoa count along with NH₃-N concentration (Abdallah Sallam *et al.*, 2011). Essential oils from oregano and white thyme, when were tested in four doses (0, 50, 250 and 500 mg/L) in an *in-vitro* study revealed that they have the potential to modify ruminal fermentation and suppress rumen methane production without negative effects on feed digestibility, suggesting it as an alternatives to ionophores for methane reduction in beef cattle (Benetel *et al.*, 2022). Combination of Essential oils from Ceylon cinnamon, dill seeds, eucalyptus, and probably others, at low concentrations may be a pragmatic approach to reduce methane emission and nitrogen excretion from ruminant without negatively affecting feed digestion or fermentation (Cobellis *et al.*, 2016). Supplementation of 1 g/day of blend of essential oils daily in the ration of dairy cattle reduces methane production on absolute terms (l/d) and decreases the amount of methane production per unit of dry matter consumed, and the effect is sustained over time without affecting feed intake or milking performance (Bach *et al.*, 2023). When basal diet was supplemented with 200 mg and 400 mg microencapsulated blend of essential oils (MBEO)/kg dietary DM in 9 sheep, there was reduction in methane emissions (24.5 and 27.6 l/kg digestible organic matter (DOM), respectively) treatments as compared to the control group (38.2 l/kg DOM) (Soltan *et al.*, 2018). The effects of increasing concentrations (1.0, 1.5 and 2.0 g/L) of oregano (*Origanum vulgare* L.) and rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis* L.) essentials oil have also shown promising effects on ruminal gas emissions when tested *in vitro*. The maximum reduction of methane production was observed upto 72% and 9% with oregano and rosemary EO, respectively (Cobellis *et al.*, 2015). The supplementation of 0.5% orange essential oil (OEO) reduced methane emissions (g/day) by 12% without affecting the dry matter intake in heifers fed bermudagrass hay as a basal diet (Jiménez-Ocampo *et al.*, 2022). The supplementation of Essential oil blends (garlic, lemongrass, cumin, lavender, and nutmeg) and fumaric acid have shown to be an effective way to reduce greenhouse gas emission and enhance total volatile fatty acids. Compared with the control, the addition of essential

oil blends (100 µL) have shown to decrease methane production by 86.4%, and fumaric acid (3% of total mixed ration) by 90.8% in an *in vitro* study using inoculum from three rumen-cannulated Black Angus beef cows (Alabi *et al.*, 2023). Sage, pine, and clove essential oils (300, 600, and 900 mg/L) have shown positive effects on methane production and *in vitro* ruminal fermentation parameters, in an *in vitro* study using rumen inoculum from three mature Dalagh ewes (Bokharaeian *et al.*, 2023). Effects of 6 essential oils from garlic/, thyme, clove, orange peel, mint, and cinnamon in different doses (100, 200 and 300 ppm) were studied on *in vitro* rumen methane reduction and *in vitro* digestibility using *in vitro* gas production technique. All essential oils reported to have highest *in-vitro* methane reduction potential (MRP doses) at 300 ppm dose without any negative effect on *in vitro* Digestibility (Rofiq *et al.*, 2021). Essential oils from *Origanum vulgare* and *Thymus vulgaris* (3 mL per kg of concentrate) supplementation have no effect on *in vivo* methane emissions and rumen parameters in Nellore beef cattle (Benetel *et al.*, 2024). It is well reported that the effect of Essential oils on methane production may either due to toxicity to methanogens or reduction in H₂ production due to decreased acetate and butyrate production (i.e. reduced fibre digestion) (Kumar *et al.*, 2014). Based on the above studies, it is concluded that, a combination of several Essential oils at low doses or a combination of Essential oils with other antimethanogenic agents is an effective alternative in mitigating methane emission from ruminants (Patra and Yu, 2012).

CONCLUSION

This review article highlighted the beneficial effects of various phytogetic feed additives due to their ability to change the rumen microbial ecology and reducing methane production. These photogenic substances are derived from trees, shrubs, and legumes. In this review most of the studies conducted are *in vitro* experiments; however, to understand the efficiency of these phytogetic substances and their effects on methanogenesis, and animal performance, *in vivo* studies are needed to validate the results. These studies not only protect our environment from global warming but also enhance the farmer's income due to the organic nature of finished products.

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HOW TO CITE: Manjeet Kumar^{1*}, Tripta Devi², Suman Lata³, Mitigating Strategies For Enteric Methane Emissions In Ruminants: An Overview On Sustainable Alternatives, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2026, 3 (5), 673-682. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20280985>